

IMPROVEMENT OF MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS OF CULTURAL HERITAGE
OBJECTS IN THE REGION

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ANNOTATION: The problems of exploitation of objects of cultural heritage that characterize the subject of this study are covered. Features of the classification of objects of cultural heritage and their identification in different countries are presented. A separate and fundamental issue of the management of objects of cultural heritage is security activities based on unique models formed by different countries based on their experiences.

KEYWORDS: the object of cultural heritage, architectural monuments, State observation, digital technologies of the object of cultural heritage.

Introduction.

Joint product of human and natural creation, as well as areas with historical, archaeological, urban planning, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological value, including places of folk crafts, historical settlements or centers of urban planning and historical (including military) events, monuments, famous buildings related to the lives of historical figures, memorial sites, natural landscapes, as well as cultural layers, remains of buildings of old cities, towns, settlements, residences, places where rituals are performed.¹

Certain buildings, buildings and structures of historical, scientific, artistic or special cultural value, works of painting, sculpture, applied decorative arts related to them, and the historical composition of these buildings, buildings and structures territories, as well as memorial houses, apartments, cemeteries, mausoleums and some graves, monumental works of art, objects of science and technology (including military equipment), anthropology, ethnography, numismatics, epigraphy, cartography, photographic materials, motion pictures, audio-, video recordings and recordings on other bodies, works of literature and art, archival, manuscript and drawing documents, ancient manuscript books, early typescript books, rare and rare editions, sheet music, sacred objects and memorials objects, stone sculptures, rock carvings, archaeological monuments.

There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in Uzbekistan, such as historical monuments, monuments built by the great talent of our great ancestors, sacred sites, and most of them are included in the UNESCO list. Therefore, in recent years, our country has adopted many regulatory legal documents on the development of this direction. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 "On measures to further improve the state management system in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage" No. PF-6199, the Cultural Heritage Agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports done. The fact that the main tasks of the agency, such as the identification, accounting, protection

¹ <https://lex.uz/acts/-25461>

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and promotion of the objects of material cultural heritage, such as maintaining the state register, electronic catalog, state cadastre, defining the protected areas, and implementing state control in the field, contribute to the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country. It is important to carry out systematic scientific and methodological research.

Economic factors:

- Allocation of funds and establishment of special funds for preservation and restoration of cultural monuments;
- Regulation and moderation of the prices of existing services;
- Reduction of taxes on cultural objects;
- Implementation of measures to increase (diversify) the type of tourist products and services;
- Creating a competitive environment in the industry;
- The economic crisis caused by the pandemic; - Increase in income and standard of living of the population.

The problem of preservation of cultural heritage objects is one of the most difficult problems in scientific and practical activities in the field of construction.

Social factors:

- the population's fixed ideas about values, their attitude to the preservation of cultural heritage and their religious beliefs;
- traditions and values formed in the population;
- development of social infrastructure;
- training of qualified personnel;
- activities of non-governmental non-commercial organizations;
- training of guides and specialists;
- providing quality and exemplary service to local and foreign tourists

Technological factors:

- advertising of historical architectural monuments through the Internet and other mass media;
- creation and regular enrichment of websites for the study of historical and cultural heritage;
- organization of Wi-Fi internet zones in cultural and historical objects and museums;
- the use of innovative technologies for the protection of archaeological monuments;
- use of digital technologies in establishing the activities of existing museums in the region;
- creation of a single database of all historical and cultural resource reserves - organization of virtual tourist tours, etc.

Great interest in cultural heritage preservation is primarily related to the risk of object loss associated with various factors of natural decay and various types of destruction of artificial nature. Another important issue is the effective use of cultural heritage potential for economic and social development of regions.

The research topic, which determines the problem area of the research, is the process of timely implementation of measures to prevent the destruction and loss, repair or reconstruction of the object.

The purpose of the study is to improve the mechanism of managing the operation of conservatory objects, taking into account the necessary capital and restoration work in a modern digital environment. Development of digital model elements for predicting reconstruction

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measures Real estate historically associated with a specific area, works of art of special importance as a result of historical events.

Historically important for all mankind and of great importance in human cultural development and preservation of memory for future generations These include: architectural monuments; natural complexes; works of art; archaeological objects and other objects inherited from the past and of historical value. Architectural monuments include separately built (immovable) buildings and structures of special importance for the country's culture and history.

Preservation of heritage is the most important condition for the economic development of any country, therefore there is a need for state regulation in the field of protection, disposal and use of material cultural heritage.

The study is based on the materials of the national and international legal framework in the field of urban planning and cultural heritage protection. The main document is the Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural Heritage of the XVII Session of the General Conference of UNESCO.

Activities for the preservation of cultural monuments are also carried out by specialized state organizations with the participation of state funds. Currently, cultural heritage includes monuments and places of interest that are directly related to the history of society and the state and have historical and cultural significance.

Registers, catalogs, systematization and inventory of historical monuments and production in all countries. Some of these databases contain certain information about computerized activities. In the legislation of foreign countries, two main rights are related to the concept of "historical and cultural monument". In order to recognize an object as a monument in the generality of countries, it is enough to have special, cultural, scientific and other qualities that allow it to be established as a separate part of the national heritage.

Activities in the field of preservation of cultural heritage objects are of special importance for the state and society, as well as in determining the direction of development of state policy and the goals of the activities of state authorities.

Research to determine the following issues in the management of residential activities:

- limiting the participation of regional operators in the restoration of cultural heritage objects;
- financing problem;
- the problem of meeting the requirements of security obligations;
- the problem is in the estimated rate for repair and restoration work.

Development of a conceptual model of effective management of cultural heritage objects in the context of digitization and description of the main stages of the introduction of innovative technologies for the creation and use of an operational digital model of the building. The use of digital technologies can be the basis for assessing the dilapidated condition of the object and planning the timely financing of the necessary amount of repair, restoration and restoration work.

As a result of the theoretical and practical study of increasing the economic efficiency of the industry, the following conclusions were reached and recommendations were developed: improving quality and exemplary service to museums and objects of cultural heritage and thereby strengthening their reputation, organizing cultural events such as international exhibitions, conferences, festivals in order to present the historical heritage of the country on the world tourist market, in the field of historical cultural tourism of archaeological monuments by significantly

increasing their role, bringing them to a brand level among foreign and local tourists, preparing archaeological monuments for museum exhibitions by partial (conservation and restoration), organizing master classes for tourists in folk art centers to introduce the traditions of national crafts to the world, to increase the visit of foreign tourists to historical and cultural objects, to organize high-quality excursion services by qualified specialists, to promote the activities of tourist information centers related to historical and cultural tourism, to provide scientific and popular information from radio, television and Internet networks make it widely available.

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